

PRIORITY AREAS OF DEVELOPMENT OF "GREEN ECONOMY" IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the priority directions and characteristics of the development of the "green economy" in Uzbekistan.

Key words and phrases: Green economy, digital economy, green energy, investment, natural resources.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va xususiyatlari taxlil qilinadi.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: Yashil iqtisodiyot, raqamli iqtisodiyot, yashil energetika, investitsiya, tabiiy resurslar.

The appearance of the world changed significantly in the 20th century. In 1900, the world population was 1.6 billion. person, in 2000 this indicator was 6 billion. people, and by 2017 the population of the earth will be 7.6 billion. is organizing a person. The average life expectancy of the population has almost doubled worldwide, and the poverty rate has decreased by more than 3 times. Economic development and rapid growth of the population's standard of living under the influence of scientific and technical achievements have led to a rapid increase in the world's population. Advances in science and technology have ensured higher rates of economic development than the rate of growth of the world's population. For example, during the 20th century, the world's population increased by 3.6 times, while the world gross domestic product increased by more than 18 times.

These problems can be solved through the development of "green economy". These problems are also important for our country, and therefore serious importance is attached to the development of the "green economy" in our country, and as mentioned above, the "green economy" the development strategy is useful in achieving these goals. According to him, a number of directions have been set in this regard.

According to the list of investment projects for the development of renewable energy, the total cost in 2017-2025 is 5.3 billion. It is planned to implement 810 projects worth USD. In 2017-2021, measures to develop the use of renewable energy sources and increase energy efficiency in economic sectors and the social sphere, including the development of normative legal documents, targeted programs and 28 measures to implement other priority tasks caught. 49.3% of the financing of these projects was carried out by enterprises' own funds, 40.8% by foreign investments and loans, 7.3% by the Republic of

Uzbekistan Recovery and Development Fund, 2.6% by credit resources of commercial banks. is increased. The analysis of the technological composition of the projects shows that 79.3% of them are new construction projects, and 20.7% are modernization projects.

The widespread introduction of green economy requires the modernization of the household utility system. For this, it is necessary to implement passive solar heating technology, use renewable energy resources in buildings, and reform the heating system. The reforms carried out in this direction will make it possible to create 15,000 new jobs by 2020, and 120,000 by 2050.

The transition to a market economy through sustainable and efficient use of natural and energy resources will allow Uzbekistan to reduce environmental pollution, adapt to climate change, and increase its ability to respond effectively to natural disasters. In this way, the country can abandon the path of economic growth due to the extensive use of hydrocarbon resources and become the leader of the "green" economy in Central Asia.

"The World Bank is pleased to support Uzbekistan in the development of the "green" economy. We will continue our work with the Government and further develop the cooperation of interested state bodies, international organizations, financial institutions and other parties in this direction. We have implemented a number of joint activities together with ITKVV and other partners. For example, earlier we published: "Uzbekistan: choosing an innovative and "green" future", a long-term strategy report on institutional assessment of climate and environment and decarbonization of the national economy. - said Marco Mantovanelli, head of the World Bank office in Uzbekistan. "The new cooperation program of the World Bank Group with Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 envisages additional financial and analytical support for the government's efforts to develop the "green" economy."

Every country strives to ensure sustainable economic growth, because economic growth:

1. to increase the volume of national product and income;
2. efficient use of resources;
3. to the emergence of new needs and opportunities;
4. increases the prestige of the country in international markets and, most importantly, ensures the well-being of the population.

In a word, all economic reforms implemented are aimed at only one goal - to increase the well-being of the population, improve the way of life and please our people.

In the regions of our republic, reserves for the use of energy from renewable energy sources have not yet been fully utilized, and there is a need to develop regionally targeted programs for them. However, there are great opportunities to use alternative and renewable energy sources in our country. Let's say that the main part of the year in our republic is 300 sunny days, according to experts, its power is equal to 50 trillion 973 million tons of conventional fuel, which is much more than the total energy reserves identified in our country. In addition, the natural conditions of our country are favorable for the combined use of solar and wind energy. Especially in our country, there are wide opportunities for the development of small-scale alternative energy sources. There is a high possibility of building "solar houses" in our country of Serkuyosh, providing them with solar heating, hot water and photoelectric energy. Development of innovative projects aimed at using environmentally friendly energy sources in our country, including domestic and foreign ones the broad involvement of investment sources will adequately serve to ensure the prospects of this sector.

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